

Assessment of Online Facilitation for Teaching and Learning Processes among Facilitators in National Open University of Nigeria

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to assess the online facilitation teaching and learning processes among facilitators in the National Open University of Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted for the study. Three research questions were answered and one hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study comprised all the facilitators and learners across study centres of the National Open University of Nigeria across the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. 44 facilitators and 161 learners were purposively selected for participation in the study. Cronbach Alpha reliability test was used to determine the internal consistency of the two instruments (Online Facilitation Assessment Questionnaire (OFAQ) for facilitators and then for learners) which yielded reliability coefficients of 0.929 and 0.846 respectively. Frequencies, percentages, mean and standard deviation statistics were used to answer the research questions, and t-test statistics to test the hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. Findings from the study revealed that there is no significant difference between online facilitation skills possessed by male and female academic staff. The conclusion from the study is that facilitators to a high extent possessed the technical, communication, and class management skills required for effective online facilitation exercise and the difference in skills possessed by both male and female facilitators is not statistically significant. It was therefore recommended that the NOUN approach of training, re-training and follow-up services by a team of experts and technical staff be replicated in other institutions.

Keyword: Assessment, Online Facilitation, Competencies, Gender, National Open University of Nigeria.

Introduction

The National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) seeks to bring education closer to multitudes of Nigerians, who do not have the privilege of pursuing full-time university programmes. NOUN's unique principle is flexibility. Flexibility helps to accommodate students, irrespective of their workplace situation, location or circumstance. This principle of flexibility coupled with the Covid-19 pandemic that has necessitated a new normal makes online facilitation the only visible option for instructional delivery in NOUN. For efficiency, assessment of its processes and implementation, especially as it affects facilitators' capability is therefore desirable at this time.

Online facilitation (also referred to as online teaching and learning) can be described as a Computer-Mediated, Web-based learning environment. It therefore requires facilitators with appropriate skills to drive (Setlhako, 2014; Angeli, Valamedes & Bonk, 2003). According to Gustafon and Gibbs (2000) as well as Martin, Wang and Sandaf (2020), successful online facilitators need to learn strategies to make the process learner-friendly and also devise ways of engaging learners sufficiently in the learning process. Online facilitation therefore requires that the facilitator or instructor apply multiple strategies to facilitate the student's learning and critical thinking skills (Richardson et al, 2015; Schinder & Burkholder, 2014); improve the student's sense of community (Rovai, 2007); and promote students' connectedness and learning (Shea, Li & Pickett, 2006). The role of an online facilitator has therefore shifted from just being a subject expert that dishes out the content to the learners, to someone who facilitates learning. For a successful online facilitation process, the facilitator in addition to being a subject expert should be able to display some technical competencies (Haruna & Hassan, 2017).

Technical competencies require a facilitator to be able to operate a computer and some necessary tools such as the Internet, e-mails, zoom etc. (Setlhako, 2014). According to Gulbahar and Kalelioglu (2015, competent electronic instructors are key to successful online learning implementation. Alqahtani & Rajkhan (2020) in a study of critical success factors for e-learning during the COVID-19 pandemic found technology management to be one of them. Campbell and Cameron (2016)

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also submit that digital teachers must be able to educate students in a virtual environment using emerging digital technologies. On the facilitation platform of the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN), some of the technical skills where competencies are required include recording virtual class conversations, creating and uploading interactive videos, initiating and coordinating interactive forums, setting up a virtual library on the course page etc. Therefore, for this study, the required competencies investigated include recording virtual class conversations, creating and uploading interactive videos, initiating and coordinating interactive forums, setting up the virtual library on the course page etc. It is expected and important that these tools are used to help learners become comfortable during the online course as they increase students' learning and engagement (Martin, Wang & Sadaf, 2018). Using synchronous tools such as audio, video, text, etc. provides opportunities for interaction between facilitators and learners, assists students to grasp the instructional content better and connects with their instructors (Martin and Parker, 2014; Borup et al, 2015).

According to Xie and Derakhshan (2021), learning is beyond mere exposure to information, it encompasses social, psychological and emotional interactions. Strachan (2020) therefore opines that effective instruction is usually actualised within the positive teacher-student relationship context. According to Frisby (2019), and Mercer and Dornyei (2020), teachers should be approachable, believe in all their students, be empathetic, be responsive to each student's individuality, support students' autonomy and be passionate about their profession. For this, according to Mercer and Dornyei (2020), teachers take different actions such as taking care of their talk, being careful about feedback to students, listening to learners, employing questions to engage students and rethinking classroom management as managing relationships. All the above can be summed up in one word "communication". Communication is one essential skill for classroom efficiency both in the face-to-face and online modes.

In online facilitation, the learner and the facilitator in most cases are far apart, therefore, securing and sustaining the attention of the learner requires effectiveness in communication (Haruna & Hassan, 2017). According to Halias, Ismail and Baharudin (2017), the facilitation process cannot be effectively done without effective communication. Christen, Kelly, Fall and Snyder (2015), submit that students appreciate online instructors who are responsive to their needs, engage in frequent communication strategies, use visibility strategies and share personal information. Asha (2020) conducted a study on students' perceptions towards online classes and their effectiveness in enhancing active participation and communication skills. Findings from the study revealed that students agreed unanimously that to a greater extent, online classes enhance speaking and listening skills. They also agreed that online classes enhance participation as well as communication. Cakiroglu (2014) also observed a highly satisfactory percentage in terms of assessing communication between teachers and students in online classes.

Observation and experience have shown that in the face-to-face mode of teaching, the need for classroom management is key as it determines how successful the class session will be. Classroom management has been a consistent concern to educators and researchers because it plays a critical role in facilitating effective learning. According to Gold, Pfirmann & Holodynski (2021), classroom management is an important skill for the academic, social-emotional and motivational development of students and the health of teachers. Adedigba and Sulaiman (2020) therefore submits that teachers must have classroom management skills to successfully build a secure and effective learning environment for pupils' quality education. Babadjanova (2020) defines classroom management as a wide variety of skills and techniques that teachers use to keep students organized, focused and academically predictive during a class. Decades back, the physical classroom setting dominated our educational system. However, after the advent of the COVID-19 pandemic, the virtual classroom system became a phenomenon in our mode of educational delivery in Nigeria. In particular, the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) now operates a virtual classroom system for the facilitation of all her courses. Just as in the physical classroom setting virtual classrooms which also involve pedagogical interactions also require effective classroom management (Oparaji, Igbokwe & Ugwu, 2020).

According to Bigne, Badenes, Ruiz and Andreu (2018), if a teacher possesses technical and affective skills and is familiar with the tools and functionalities that a virtual classroom offers, learner engagement can be enhanced and this would minimize untoward behaviour among learners in a virtual classroom. Kavrayici (2021) carried out a study on the relationship between classroom management and a sense of classroom community in a graduate virtual classroom. The findings of the study showed that various dimensions of classroom management considered (leadership, motivation, rules and behaviour management, communication, instructional planning and implementation and organisational dimensions) were positively correlated with connectedness and learning dimensions of the classroom community. Milliken (2019) found that when leaders implement an instructional approach in managing learner behaviour in a virtual classroom, the learners' pro-social behaviour is enhanced and academic engagement across all learning areas is increased. Sibanda (2021) carried out a study on private school teachers' classroom management in a virtual classroom. The result of the study revealed that private high school teachers adopted diverse strategies to manage learners' behaviour in a virtual classroom. The result also indicated that teachers use

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strategies such as collaborative learning, they also prepare all the materials required according to the set scheme of work, plan the learning activities which are exciting and use interactive learner-centred approaches which engage learners all the time. Teachers who manage learners' behaviour must actively engage them in meaningful and challenging educational experiences (Moore & Hansen, 2012).

The National Open University of Nigeria is the leading ODL University, providing online facilitation in Nigeria. To play this role well, the institution's Online Facilitation System must be efficient. The efficiencies expected cannot be, unless the facilitators are competent in their roles. The roles are numerous and cannot be covered extensively in a single research work. At the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) currently; three aspects of the skills needed by facilitators are prominent and call for immediate investigation. These are; facilitators' skills in the use of technological tools for facilitation (such as recording virtual class conversation, creating interactive videos for asynchronous facilitation, creating announcements on the course page, setting up Zoom online classes etc etc.), communication during online classes and class management in the online class. It is on this note, that this research work assessed the online facilitation process of the National Open University of Nigeria, with a focus on facilitators' competencies in online technology use for various functions, effective communication and class management in online classes.

Gender generally is always an issue in educational research. Shea (2007) in a study explored instructors' motivations to teach online and found that female faculty members were more attracted to online teaching than their male counterparts. Ganji and Sejjehie (2022) found a significant effect of gender on the scores of participants in classroom management behaviour. Men and women were found to be using different classroom management strategies. Martin, Yin and Mayall (2006) found a significant difference between males and females with regards to the instruction management subscale on the inventory. Female teachers were seen to favour interventionist behaviour more than their male counterparts. Nejati, Hassani and Sahrapour (2014) however found that gender is not significantly related to classroom management among a sample of Iranian EFL teachers of a private English institute. Since the gender of facilitators as discovered from research and experience can play an important role in their online facilitation, having a clear picture of how it affects facilitators' technical competencies is essential. Therefore, in this study, one hypothesis was tested to investigate the differences in the competencies of male and female participants.

Many of the studies reviewed attempted to investigate technical competencies, communication and classroom management skills possessed by online facilitators using quantitative measures through interview schedules with the facilitators themselves. This study however attempted to get the learners that were taught to rate their facilitators on their communication and classroom management skills. Studies that used this approach are very rare in literature. It is on this note that this study sought to investigate the technical competencies in handling virtual learning technological tools, communication and classroom management skills possessed by male and female facilitators in the National Open University of Nigeria online facilitation system, to make informed recommendations for improved performance by facilitators in NOUN and by extension in various universities that look up to the university for mentorship in the virtual classroom facilitation system in Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

1. Assess the level of competence of online facilitators to carry out teaching and learning activities required for effective online facilitation in NOUN.
2. Assess the level of communication skills explored by facilitators during online teaching and learning activities in NOUN.
3. Examine the level of online classroom management skills explored by facilitators in NOUN.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of competency displayed by online facilitators during teaching and learning activities in NOUN?
2. How effective are the facilitators in their communication skills during online teaching and learning activities in NOUN?
3. What is the level of online classroom management skills explored by facilitators in NOUN?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the online facilitation skills displayed by male and female facilitators during online teaching and learning activities in NOUN.

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Methodology

A survey research design was adopted for the study. Academic staff at the university headquarter in Abuja and students from the various centres within the Abuja metropolis formed the sample for the study. The facilitators at the headquarters were used for the study because they have access to the technical staff at the Learner Content Management System (LCMS) directorate, and the various facilities such as studio room, whiteboard and other sophisticated tools. Therefore, they have all that is required to respond to the items in the questionnaire. For a similar reason, learners at the various centres within the Abuja metropolis were used as respondents for the study. A purposive sampling technique was used to select respondents from both facilitators and learners. Owing to the nature of the institution (Open and Distance Learning) both facilitators and learners are not always available at the same time. Sometimes staff have official duties outside the headquarters and deliver lectures, and attend meetings from where they are through virtual means. For learners, owing to the flexibility of the programme; they do not have to come to the centre most times before they do what they need to do. In view of this, staff and students that were available at the time of study were used. Since it is not ethical to force people to participate in a study like this, among those available, only those who were willing eventually participated in the study. In all 205 people participated in the study (44 facilitators and 161 learners).

The research instrument used was titled Facilitators Online Facilitation Assessment Questionnaire (FOFAQ) for facilitators and then for learners. Learners Online Facilitation Assessment Questionnaire (LOFAQ) for learners required that they rate their facilitators' communication skills and class management in Online Facilitation on a Four-Points scale instrument labelled Strongly Agreed (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The facilitators self-assessed their level of competency in accessing and navigating through the online facilitation environment in order to help students learn. Their responses were to be made on a five-point likert scale instrument using; Extremely Competent (EC), Moderately Competent (MC), Somewhat Competent (SC), Slightly Competent (SLC), Not Competent (NC). The research instrument was validated by experts. Corrections made were effected before the instruments were administered to the sampled respondents. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach alpha reliability test. The reliability index of the instrument for facilitators and learners were found to be 0.846 and 0.929 respectively; thus portraying a high level of internal consistency and as such the instruments were found usable for the study. The data gathered was analysed using frequency, percentages, means, standard deviation for the three research questions, while independent sample t-test analysis was used to test the only hypothesis that guided the study.

Results

Frequency counts, percentages, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while independent sample t-test was used for testing the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question 1

Research Question One: What is the level of competency displayed by online facilitators during teaching and learning activities in NOUN?

Table 1: Level of Facilitators' Competency for Online Facilitation in NOUN

Level of competency of facilitators	NC	SLC	SC	MC	EC	Mean	St. Dev.
Facilitate and record the virtual class conversation.	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (6.8)	20 (45.5)	21 (47.7)	4.41	0.622
Create interactive videos for asynchronous facilitation.	2(4.5)	0 (0.0)	4 (9.1)	22 (50.0)	16 (36.4)	4.14	0.930
Lead forum discussions.	1(2.3)	2 (4.5)	6 (13.6)	19 (43.2)	16 (36.4)	4.07	0.950
Lead chat forums.	1(2.3)	2 (4.5)	8 (18.2)	20 (45.5)	13 (29.5)	3.95	0.939
Set-up 'meet your facilitator page' on the course page.	1(2.3)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	20 (45.5)	23 (52.3)	4.45	0.730

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Create announcement on the course page.	1(2.3)	0 (0.0)	4 (9.1)	15 (34.1)	24(54.5)	4.39	0.841
Prepare a lesson plan for online facilitation on the course page.	1(2.3)	1 (2.3)	1 (2.3)	20 (45.5)	21 (47.7)	4.34	0.834
Set up a virtual library on the course page.	2(4.5)	1 (2.3)	5 (11.4)	17 (38.6)	19 (43.2)	4.14	1.025
Create introductory videos on the course page.	1(2.3)	1 (2.3)	2 (4.5)	17 (38.6)	23(52.3)	4.36	0.865
Set up zoom online class on the course page.	1(2.3)	0 (0.0)	4 (9.1)	14 (31.8)	25(56.8)	4.41	0.844
Use whiteboard in the zoom class.	3(6.8)	8 (18.2)	5 (11.4)	20 (45.5)	8(18.2)	3.50	1.191
Create a discussion forum on the course page.	1(2.3)	0 (0.0)	6 (13.6)	12 (27.3)	25(56.8)	4.36	0.892

Percentages in parenthesis

KEY: **NC** – Not Competent; **SLC** – Slightly Competent; **SC** – Somewhat Competent; **MC** – Moderately Competent; **EC** – Extremely Competent

Source: Field Work 2022

Table 1 above shows the level of competency of facilitators in the identified skills required for online facilitation in the teaching and learning process in NOUN. More than half of the respondents accepted all twelve (12) items as true. Those who agreed and strongly agreed with each of the twelve (12) items are above 50%. The mean ratings of each of the twelve (12) items are each above the 3.00 benchmark for the acceptance of a statement on a five-Likert scale. This is a confirmation of the result found from the frequency and percentage analyses. Conclusively, in the opinion of the majority of the respondents; who are academic staff on the level of competency of facilitators in the identified online facilitation skills in NOUN, they agree that they are competent in the following identified technical skills required for online facilitation processes; Facilitation and recording of the virtual class conversation, creating interactive videos for asynchronous facilitation, leading forum discussions, leading chat forums, setting up ‘meet your facilitator page’ on the course page, creating announcement on the course page, preparing a lesson plan for online facilitation on the course page, setting up a virtual library on the course page, creating introductory videos on the course page, setting up zoom online class on the course page, using a whiteboard in the zoom class and creating a discussion forum on the course page.

Research Question Two: How effective are the facilitators in their communication skills during online teaching and learning activities in NOUN?

Table 2: Facilitators’ Communication Skills During Online Teaching and Learning Activities in NOUN

Level of agreement that facilitators possess the listed skills	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	St. Dev.
The facilitator uses language appropriate for the students.	0(0.0)	2 (1.2)	95 (59.0)	64 (39.8)	3.39	0.513
The facilitator’s introduction of lesson is always interesting.	1(0.6)	8 (5.0)	102 (63.4)	50 (31.1)	3.25	0.570
The facilitator asks appropriate starting questions that helps to engage the students.	0(0.0)	56 (34.8)	71 (44.1)	34 (21.1)	2.86	0.737
The facilitator asks appropriate follow up questions to sustain student’s engagement in the course.	0(0.0)	10 (6.2)	106 (65.8)	45 (28.0)	3.22	0.544

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Facilitator delivers instructions that are accurate, clear and concise.	0(0.0)	11 (6.8)	47 (29.2)	103 (64.0)	3.57	0.620
Facilitator summarises the lesson to enhance retention of the content learnt.	0(0.0)	9 (5.6)	98 (60.9)	54 (33.5)	3.28	0.561

1) Percentages in parenthesis

2) **KEY: SD** – Strongly Disagree; **D**– Disagree; **A** – Agree; **SA** – Strongly Agree

Source: Field Work 2022

Table 2 above revealed the effectiveness of the facilitators in communicating with their learners during the online class as opined by their students. More than half of the respondents agreed with all the six (6) items. Those that agreed and strongly agreed with each of the six (6) items are above 50%. The mean ratings of each of the six (6) items are each above the 2.50 benchmark for the acceptance of a statement on a four-Likert scale. This is a confirmation of the result found from the frequencies and percentages analysis.

Conclusively, in the opinion of the majority of the respondents; the following statements on the performance of the facilitators in communicating with their students during the online class are acceptable; the facilitator uses language appropriate for the students, the facilitator’s introduction of lesson is always interesting, the facilitator asks appropriate starting questions that helps to engage the students, the facilitator asks appropriate follow up questions to sustain student’s engagement in the course, facilitator delivers instructions that are accurate, clear and concise, facilitator summarises the lesson to enhance retention of the content learnt.

Research Question Three: What is the level of online classroom management skills explored by facilitators in NOUN?

Table 3: The Level of online classroom management skills explored by facilitators in NOUN

ITEM	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	St. Dev.
The facilitator ensures sessions holds in a quiet environment devoid of background noise and other distractions.	0(0.0)	15 (9.3)	73 (45.3)	73 (45.3)	3.36	0.648
The facilitator promotes confidence in their students.	1(0.6)	14 (8.7)	105 (65.2)	41 (25.5)	3.16	0.587
Facilitator collaborates with their students to ensure efficiency.	0(0.0)	17 (10.6)	106 (65.8)	38 (23.6)	3.13	0.572
The facilitator understands and consistently applies best techniques for starting the session.	0(0.0)	10 (6.2)	104 (64.6)	47 (29.2)	3.23	0.551
The facilitator understands and consistently applies best techniques for sustenance of student’s interest.	0(0.0)	12 (7.5)	109 (67.7)	40 (24.8)	3.17	0.543

1. Percentages in parenthesis

2. **KEY: SD** – Strongly Disagree; **D**– Disagree; **A** – Agree; **SA** – Strongly Agree

Source: Field Work 2022

Table 3 above showed the skills displayed by facilitators in NOUN. More than half of the respondents agreed with all five (5) items. Those that agreed and strongly agreed with each of the five (5) items are above 50%. The mean ratings of each of the five (5) items are each above the 2.50 benchmark for the acceptance of a statement in a four-likert scale. This is a confirmation of the result found from the frequency and percentages analysis.

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Conclusively, in the opinion of the majority of the respondents; the following statements on the classroom management displayed by facilitators in NOUN are true; the facilitators ensure sessions holds in a quiet environment devoid of background noise and other distractions, the facilitators promote confidence in their students, facilitators collaborate with their students to ensure efficiency, the facilitators understand and consistently apply best techniques for starting the session, the facilitators understand and consistently apply best techniques for sustenance of students’ interest.

Hypothesis 1

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the online facilitation skills displayed by male and female facilitators during online teaching and learning activities in NOUN.

Table 4: T-Test Analysis of Difference in Online Facilitation Skills Across Gender

GROUP	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Remark
Male	26	49.77	10.041	-0.689	42	0.495	NS
Female	18	51.61	6.289				

Source: Field Work 2022

Table 4 above presents the t-test comparison of online facilitation skills possessed by male and female facilitators. The t-test comparison showed that the difference in the online facilitation skills possessed by male and female academic staff was not statistically significant. This is evident from the sig-2 tailed value that is more than the 0.05 benchmark. Since the sig-value of t-test comparison of means of two groups which is more than the 0.05 benchmark signifies a no significant difference in online facilitation skills possessed by male and female facilitators, it therefore follows that the difference is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between online facilitation skills possessed by male and female academic staff is accepted. The values of the mean online facilitation skills possessed by female academic staff is higher than that of their male counterparts. Since the difference is not statistically significant, it can therefore not be generalized. The difference observed might have occurred due to sampling error.

Discussion of Findings

The sampled facilitators are competent in using the twelve (12) identified tools for online facilitation. Some of these include; setting up a zoom class, recording, initiating and coordinating discussion forum, chat etc. This is encouraging. The high competency might be because of the regular trainings and accessible for online facilitation. At the beginning of every semester, facilitators are usually given refresher training. Technical staff are also allocated to faculties for consultations during the facilitation period. In addition, modern computers equipped with all the software needed, studio for recording, as well as internet access are accessible to facilitators at the headquarters. The training and follow up opportunities as well as the enabling facilities and resources must have contributed to the high rating of facilitators’ competency in handling facilitation tools.

The areas the respondents displayed competencies include setting up a zoom class, recording, initiating and coordinating discussion forum, leading chat forum, creating announcement page, setting up zoom class for online lesson etc etc. All these contribute immensely to making the learning process learner-friendly and engaging. Findings from this study therefore agrees with the submission of Gustafon and Gibbs (2000) and Martin, Wang and Sandaf (2020) who emphasised the need for successful online facilitators to learn strategies to make the process learner-friendly and also devise ways of engaging learners sufficiently in the learning process. The findings of the study also agree with Richardson et al, (2015); Schinder & Burkholder, (2014) who opined that online facilitator or instructor must apply multiple strategies to facilitate learning and critical thinking skills. It also correlates with Rovai (2007) that online facilitation ought to improve student sense of community and Shea, Li & Pickett, (2006), that it should promote students’ connectedness and learning. A number of scholars submitted that when facilitators are competent in the various identified skills required for online learning, students will be better engaged and it becomes easy for students to understand learning materials (Berge, 2008; Martin, Wang & Sadaf, 2014; Martin and Parker, 2014; Borup et al, 2015; Rose, 2009).

Learners while rating their facilitators both on communication and class management agreed that the facilitators did well in all the identified areas of both communication and class management. As it applies to competency in online facilitation skills, the same explanation of regular training, as well as availability and unrestricted accessibility to enabling facilities and resources is a possible explanation. Various scholars also agree that possession of these competencies by facilitators, will bring about satisfaction of students with the process and also encourage collaboration (Eskey and Schulte, 2010; Swan, 2001). However, the research showed that a particular item - “the facilitators ask appropriate starting questions that helps to engage

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the students”, attracted a disagree of about 35.0%. The implication of this is that a sizeable number of the facilitators are weak in asking appropriate starting questions that helps to engage the learners.

The findings of this study agrees with the submission of Cakiroglu (2014) that there is a highly satisfactory percentage in terms of assessing communication between teachers and students in online classes. Mercer and Dornyei (2020), also corroborate this view that teachers ought to take different actions such as taking care of their talk, being careful about feedback to students, listening to learners, employing questions to engage students and rethinking classroom managements as managing relationships. Communication is one essential skill for classroom efficiency both in the face to face and online mode. Particularly in online facilitation, the learner and the facilitator in most cases are far apart, therefore, securing and sustaining the attention of the learner require effectiveness in communication. Halias, Ismail and Baharudin (2017) as well as Christen, Kelly, Fall and Snyder (2015) both summed it up that facilitation process cannot be effectively done without effective communication. And that students appreciate online instructors who are responsive to their needs, engage in frequent communication strategies, use visibility strategies and share personal information.

The areas of classroom management studied included; facilitators ensuring sessions holds in a quiet environment devoid of background noise and other distractions, promoting confidence in their learners, collaborating with their students to ensure efficiency, understanding and consistently applying best techniques for starting the session and understanding and consistently applying best techniques for sustenance of learners’ interest. The facilitators’ high rating in classroom management as evident from the result can also be attributed to regular trainings and retraining as well as follow up monitoring from technical staff and experts. Findings from this study agrees with Sibanda (2021) in a study on private school teachers’ classroom management in a virtual classroom. The result revealed that private high school teachers adopted diverse strategies to manage learners’ behaviour in a virtual classroom. The result also indicated that teachers use strategies such as collaborative learning, they also prepare all the materials required according to the set scheme of work, plan the learning activities which are exciting and use interactive learner-centred approaches which engage learners all the time. Teachers who would manage learners’ behaviour must actively engage them in meaningful and challenging educational experiences (Moore and Hansen, 2012).

Gender differences in the possession of identified online facilitation skills showed a difference that is not statistically significant. In this study however female participants had higher score. A closer look showed that the male’s standard deviation was higher, meaning that their mean score in identified online facilitation skill may not be the true representation. Some men might have scored very high while some scored very low. The difference however is not significant and so not generalisable. The findings of this study however disagree with findings of some scholars (Shea, 2007; Ganji & Seizeihe, 2022; Martin, Yin & Mayall, 2006 and Seaman, 2009).

Conclusion

This study sought to assess the online facilitation teaching and learning processes among facilitators at the National Open University of Nigeria. Specifically, the level of competence, communication and online classroom management skills of online facilitators to carry out teaching and learning activities in NOUN were explored. Findings showed that the participants of the study displayed a high level of competence, communication and efficient classroom management skills were displayed by them during online teaching and learning activities in NOUN. Also, the difference in competence displayed by male and female facilitators was not statistically significant. Findings from this study showed that NOUN facilitators at the headquarters were highly competent in the identified skills; they were also rated by their learners to be highly effective in communication and classroom management. This suggests that, with enough and regular training and retraining, along with the availability of support staff as well as accessibility to enabling facilities and resources obtainable in NOUN and as enjoyed by the respondents; efficiency in online facilitation is attainable. However, many students particularly disagreed that “the facilitators ask appropriate starting questions that help to engage the students”.

Recommendations

In view of the above, it is therefore recommended that:

- i. The model of operation in NOUN be studied by other Universities for implementation in their institutions.
- ii. Provision of and accessibility to enabling facilities and resources and services of support personnel should be extended to staff outside the headquarters.
- iii. The Nigerian University Commission (NUC) should also collaborate with NOUN to ensure that pieces of training given to NOUN staff are passed down to other Universities.

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- iv. Subsequent training of facilitators in NOUN should lay more emphasis on asking appropriate starting questions that help to engage the students.
- v. All the recommendations above should be effected equally on both male and female facilitators since there is no difference in competencies manifested across genders.

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